

Perspective

Reading the repertoire: Progress in adaptive immune receptor analysis using machine learning

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SUMMARY

The adaptive immune system holds invaluable information on past and present immune responses in the form of B and T cell receptor sequences, but we are limited in our ability to decode this information. Machine learning approaches are under active investigation for a range of tasks relevant to understanding and manipulating the adaptive immune receptor repertoire, including matching receptors to the antigens they bind, generating antibodies or T cell receptors for use as therapeutics, and diagnosing disease based on patient repertoires. Progress on these tasks has the potential to substantially improve the development of vaccines, therapeutics, and diagnostics, as well as advance our understanding of fundamental immunological principles. We outline key challenges for the field, highlighting the need for software benchmarking, targeted large-scale data generation, and coordinated research efforts.

INTRODUCTION AND PURPOSE OF THIS PERSPECTIVE

The adaptive immune system maintains a historical record of all encountered pathogens through immunological memory, which is encoded within cells expressing highly diverse adaptive immune receptors (AIRs), namely B cell receptors (BCRs, or antibodies) and T cell receptors (TCRs). These cell-surface receptors equip B cells and T cells to recognize specific antigens. Given the pivotal role of the adaptive immune system in preserving homeostasis and eliminating—or, in the case of autoimmunity, perpetuating—disease, the information encoded within an AIR repertoire (AIRR) represents a potential treasure trove of biomarkers and therapeutics. Therefore, deciphering and leveraging AIR-encoded information holds promise for not only deepening our understanding of immunological processes but also for developing more effective preventive and therapeutic interventions.¹ However, despite substantial efforts to apply machine learning (ML) to unlock the information in repertoires and receptors, performance remains low for many important prediction and generation tasks (Figure 1). In this perspective, we summarize recent progress and highlight possible paths forward. To avoid redundancy, we refer the reader to introductory and advanced texts on AIRR biology^{1–5} and ML applied to AIR(R)s.^{6–9}

MAJOR AIRR-ML AREAS AND ASSOCIATED CHALLENGES

Most ML models for receptors and repertoires fall into one of three kinds of tasks: (1) predicting antigen specificity or other

properties of individual receptors (hereafter termed *receptor classification*, Figures 1A–1D), (2) generating new receptor sequences with desired properties (*receptor generation*, Figures 1E–1G), and (3) predicting properties of an entire repertoire, such as whether an individual has an autoimmune disease (*repertoire classification*, Figure 1H). Progress on antigen specificity prediction—the core unsolved problem of the field—would have important impacts on our ability to address any of these kinds of problems.

Several factors render antigen specificity prediction (and receptor generation) challenging.¹⁰ First, there is an enormous number of possible receptors and antigens ($>10^{14}$),^{11,12} with each receptor expected to bind a range of antigen variants and vice versa.^{13–15} This diversity means that predictive models for receptor-antigen interactions need to have an extremely low false positive rate to have general utility for predicting the specificity of a single receptor. Second, whether a receptor binds an antigen depends on their overall shapes (for example, the angle formed between an antibody's heavy and light chains) but is also sensitive to fine details of the interaction interface.^{16–21} It is common for a single mutation in either a receptor or an antigen to abolish binding, as seen in SARS-CoV-2 mutations that confer resistance to monoclonal antibody therapies.²² Matching receptors to antigens therefore has aspects of both protein structure prediction and mutation effect prediction, both long-standing problems where we have only recently seen substantial progress using deep-learning systems.^{23–26} Third, the physical structure of the receptor-antigen interaction is difficult to predict due to the flexibility of the receptor complementarity-determining region (CDR) loops that usually drive the interaction. While five of

Figure 1. Progress on key AIRR analysis tasks

(A–G) Most recent work applying ML for AIRR analysis has focused on predicting properties of AIRs (A–D) or generating new AIR sequences (E–G). For both kinds of problems, important tasks have recently become tractable, although the most ambitious applications—*de novo* prediction of receptor specificity and generation of receptors against an arbitrary epitope—remain unsolved.

(H) At the repertoire level, although the detection of certain exposures using public TCRs stands out as an interesting success case, there has been less progress on more challenging tasks, such as disease diagnosis, and ML methods remain relatively primitive. This is partly due to the lack of large public training datasets and the fact that repertoire-level analyses contend with high biological uncertainty in parsing the interplay of genetics, environmental exposures, disease states, and immune responses.

the six CDR loops tend to adopt a relatively predictable conformation,^{27,28} the heavy or beta chain complementarity-determining region 3 (CDR3) loop, which is often key to antigen interactions,^{29,30} is extremely variable in structure.^{31,32} Finding (or designing) the binding pose for this loop requires navigating a large conformational space. Finally, the coevolution information that is exploited by deep learning models such as AlphaFold-Multimer (AF-M)³³ and AlphaFold3 (AF3)²⁴ to predict protein complex structures generally has less usable signal for predicting receptor/antigen interactions.³⁴

Repertoire classification (Figure 1H) faces these difficulties compounded by scale. Receptor classification approaches are generally too inaccurate to be useful in understanding repertoires. In a future where dramatic improvements in receptor specificity prediction are achieved (and paired-chain repertoire sequencing is widely available³⁵), repertoire classification might rely on the cumulative antigen-specific binding information in a given repertoire. Currently, however, most prediction efforts classify repertoires based on over-representation of certain sequences or motifs without attempting to explicitly predict the antigen specificities of each receptor.^{1,6} The signal from such approaches is generally very small (at least in the blood).^{36–39}

Repertoire sequencing is also subject to multiple sources of experimental variation (e.g., library preparation^{40,41} and DNA vs. RNA sequencing⁴²) as well as biological factors (e.g., genetic background,^{43,44} age,⁴⁵ and microbiome composition^{39,46}) that can influence and confound AIRR datasets.

To summarize, receptor and repertoire prediction tasks are currently hindered by multiple technological and biological challenges. These issues are compounded by the relatively small labeled datasets available for most predictive tasks on receptors and repertoires (Table 1).

RECEPTOR CLASSIFICATION

Receptor classification analyses aim to understand the properties of particular AIRs, especially what antigens they bind (Figures 1A–1D). Antigen specificity prediction is unsolved in the general case, although some progress has recently been made, which we will highlight.

Prediction of TCR binding

TCRs recognize peptides presented on cell surfaces by major histocompatibility complex (MHC) proteins. TCR recognition of

Table 1. Commonly used databases of immune receptors and repertoires

Database	Description	Antigen-specific	Source	Approximate size
CoV-AbDab ⁴⁷	antibodies against betacoronaviruses	yes	patents and literature	~12,000 antibodies
Immune epitope database (IEDB) ⁴⁸	BCRs and TCRs to known epitopes	yes	literature and submissions	~3,000 paired-chain BCRs; ~450 paired-chain TCRs
iReceptor ⁴⁹	BCR and TCR repertoires	no	-	~0.6 M paired-chain BCRs; ~1 B heavy-chain BCRs; ~1 M paired-chain TCRs; ~3.5 B beta-chain TCRs
McPAS-TCR ⁵⁰	pathology-associated TCRs	some	literature	~13,000 paired-chain TCRs; ~26,000 beta-chain TCRs
Observed antibody space (OAS) ⁵¹	BCRs	no	literature (reprocessed)	~2 M paired-chain BCRs; ~2 B heavy-chain BCRs
Observed T cell receptor space ⁵² (OTS)	TCRs	no	literature (reprocessed)	~1.6 M paired-chain TCRs
Patent and literature antibody database (PLAbDab) ⁵³	antibodies	some	patents and literature	~79,000 antibodies
Structural antibody database (SAbDab) ⁵⁴	antibody structures	some	PDB ⁵⁵	~6,000 antibody structures (~5,000 with antigen)
Structural T-cell receptor database (STCRDab) ⁵⁶	TCR structures	some	PDB ⁵⁵	~600 TCR structures (~400 with antigen)
VDJdb ⁵⁷	TCRs to known epitopes	yes	literature and submissions	~30,000 paired-chain TCRs for ~1,000 epitopes

Note that some databases (such as IEDB⁵⁸) curate additional kinds of information not indicated here. Abbreviations: M, millions; B, billions.

peptide-MHC (pMHC) epitopes tends to have some structural regularities. Usually, most of the contacts with the peptide are made by the CDR3 loops on the TCR.^{19,59} The space of possible pMHC epitopes is large but, in theory, can be readily enumerated, as the peptides derive directly from the primary sequence of their antigens and must bind an individual's MHC molecules, a task for which computational prediction is highly accurate.^{60–62} In principle, these factors may render the prediction problem for TCRs more tractable than for immunoglobulins, where epitope geometries are as diverse as antigen structures. However, a complicating factor is that the TCR-pMHC interaction is generally quite weak (dissociation constant is typically in the micromolar range), meaning that predictors must identify (and train on) a weaker signal.⁶³ The last several years have seen a proliferation in proposed methods for predicting TCR specificity. Here we will discuss three ongoing lines of work: (1) TCR sequence clustering methods, (2) supervised sequence-based models for specific epitopes, and (3) structure-based TCR/pMHC binding prediction.

The first real progress on TCR-pMHC binding prediction came not from supervised learning but from relatively simple schemes for clustering TCRs (Figure 1A). Clustering analyses were based on the observation that TCRs with very similar sequences often recognize the same epitope. These methods were first proposed with the emergence of large-scale unpaired sequencing of receptor chains (e.g., β -chain only) using next-generation sequencing.⁶⁴ However, more recent work has also considered paired chains.^{18,19,65} The clustering methods mostly use hand-crafted criteria and are not data-driven (i.e., there is no training step). Clustering methods enable cross-repertoire analyses of receptor sequences. As most TCR sequences are rare, exact matches are uncommon across individuals. Clusters, on the other hand, may co-occur across individuals and—depending on what other information is available—can help narrow down the cognate epitope. For example, a cluster containing TCRs deriving from multiple individuals sharing some HLA allele may indicate a possible HLA restriction for the TCRs in the cluster.^{65,66} Within an individual repertoire, the presence of a TCR cluster with more clones than expected by chance (i.e., V(D)J recombination probability) can be used to infer an antigen-directed clonal expansion⁶⁷ (Figure 1B). Clustering approaches have been usefully applied in a range of contexts.^{68–71} Popular tools include GLIPH2^{19,72} and TCRDist,¹⁸ which group TCRs based on CDR3 sequence plus V/J gene usage or the sequence similarity of all CDRs, respectively. Newer methods, such as ClusTCR,⁷³ GIANA,⁷⁴ and XTNeighbor⁷⁵ have focused on improving the computational efficiency of clustering approaches. We also note that properties of TCR clusters, such as usage of a particular V gene, tend to be more interpretable than black-box predictors and are even amenable to an information-theoretic treatment.⁷⁶ A major limitation of these approaches is, however, that they only allow for the grouping of very similar receptor sequences and thus preclude prediction for the majority of investigated sequences.

An alternative direction is to develop supervised ML models that directly predict TCR specificity using the sequences of the TCRs and their epitopes. This very active research direction has been explored in tools such as TCRex,⁷⁷ TCRGP,⁷⁷ TITAN,⁷⁸ and NetTCR,⁷⁹ among others. A representative

example is the NetTCR-2.2 tool,⁷⁹ which predicts whether a TCR will bind a specified peptide using shallow neural networks. The inputs to the model are the peptide sequence and the six CDR sequences from the alpha and beta chains of the TCR. Notably, HLA restriction is not considered. While the tool in principle is “pan-epitope,” meaning that it can be applied to epitopes not present in the training set, the NetTCR authors report that reasonable accuracy is observed only for 26 well-characterized epitopes present in the training data. Similar results were reported for another tool, MixTCRPred.⁸⁰ The MixTCRPred authors found that an experimental pan-epitope model could not generalize to unseen epitopes, leading them to focus only on “epitope-specific” prediction, in which separate neural networks are trained for each epitope of interest. These results, as well as independent benchmarks,^{81,82} indicate that trained models have not fundamentally progressed beyond clustering methods in that the models effectively predict by matching an input receptor sequence to similar receptor sequences found in the training data. Generalization to epitopes not present in the training data is not possible with any current method (Figure 1C).

An emerging line of work that could eventually achieve generalization is applying deep learning approaches to score potential TCR-pMHC pairs by modeling their three-dimensional structures (Figure 1D).^{83–85} These approaches can use information encoded in general protein structure prediction models, which are trained on much larger datasets. An example is the TCRDock tool,⁸⁵ which adapts the AF2²³ protein structure prediction model for TCR-pMHC complex prediction. TCRDock modifies the inputs to AF-M³³ to increase performance on TCR-pMHC complexes, using as input synthetic structural templates encompassing a range of possible docking geometries. The TCRmodel2 tool employs a broadly similar approach and provides a web-server interface.⁸⁶ These tools are primarily designed for investigating specific TCRs and epitopes of interest but can in principle be used to match a TCR to its antigen by treating the model confidence scores produced by AF-M as a proxy for the binding affinity between the proteins. In practice, however, they are still too slow and inaccurate to use this way. For example, TCRDock requires several minutes per candidate TCR-epitope pair, and its authors reported that the model achieved only modest accuracy (0.82 AUC) in distinguishing correct pairs from decoys.⁸⁵ As both methods are template-driven, they are also unlikely to perform well on TCRs with unusual binding geometries.^{87,88} It is also worth noting that TCR-antigen binding affinity is not a perfect proxy for T cell activation, i.e., a structural interaction does not mean that the interaction is necessarily functional. The signal sensed by T cells may be more closely related to how their TCRs disassociate from the antigen after binding, which these methods would not be expected to predict.⁸⁹

What is the best way forward? The first impediment to progress is data scarcity (Table 1). To develop predictors that generalize to unseen epitopes, the field will need more well-characterized epitopes, which we can somewhat arbitrarily define here as those with at least 100 known binding (paired-chain) TCRs. Using this definition, there are currently 30 well-characterized epitopes in VDJdb⁹⁰; recent curation efforts incorporating additional sources have not significantly expanded beyond this figure.⁸⁰ Given current data limitations, it may not be surprising

that existing models fail to generalize to unseen epitopes (and mutants thereof⁹¹). Indeed, it is difficult even to assess if one model performs better than another as test sets are too small.⁸¹ While there is no framework for estimating how many epitopes are required for generalizable prediction, it seems unlikely that substantial progress can be made without at least a few hundred and potentially a few thousand. This scale of data, however, would still be a far smaller training set than the roughly 10^5 (e.g., AF²³) to 10^{11} (e.g., the OpenAI large language models [LLMs]^{92,93}) data points used to train modern deep learning models. In addition to the insufficient scale of data, several reports have highlighted the challenges in defining negative data for the TCR-epitope prediction task.^{94–98} Negative data points are typically generated either by shuffling TCR-pMHC pairings from the positive (i.e., observed) data or by using a background dataset of unlabeled TCRs, which are assumed to bind the observed epitopes at a negligible rate.⁹⁶ The choice of negative data strategy may affect model generalization, as also seen for antibody-epitope prediction tasks.^{97,99,100}

Generalization at TCR binding prediction will also require moving beyond sequence-only training datasets. Specifically, careful integration of structural and non-structural data to train models that explicitly represent protein structure may be a way forward. For example, training sets could combine TCR-seq of tetramer-sorted cells¹⁰¹ and library assays¹⁰² such as screening TCR reactivity by yeast display of pMHC¹⁰³ with cryoelectron microscopy (cryo-EM) structures of TCR-pMHC complexes.^{104,105} Transfer learning from pre-trained protein structure predictors should also be explored further.^{106,107} New methods for protein structure prediction are also likely to drive progress. For example, existing deep learning approaches for protein structure prediction generally predict only a few possible conformations (structures) for a given set of input sequences.¹⁰⁸ Given the flexibility of CDRs, advances in the prediction of conformational ensembles may prove especially useful for AIRs.^{109–115}

Finally, to be useful at the repertoire scale, prediction will need to be fast. Model compression techniques such as distillation¹¹⁶ may be needed to create models that are practical to run on thousands of TCRs and potential epitopes.

Prediction of antibody binding

In contrast to T cell epitopes, which derive directly from an antigen’s primary sequence, antibody epitopes can potentially comprise any surface-exposed patch of an antigen in any of its conformations.¹¹⁷ We restrict our discussion here to protein antigens, as this is the most studied ML task, but note that binding predictors trained exclusively on protein antigens are unlikely to work for nucleic acids, polysaccharides, lipids, and other non-protein antigen classes. The general problem of antibody specificity prediction is unsolved: given an arbitrary antibody, one cannot predict what proteins it will bind^{3,118} (Figure 1C). However, for cases where the antigen is known, significant progress has been made in predicting the three-dimensional structure of the antibody-antigen complex. This is possible in approximately 20% of instances using publicly available models.^{119–122}

The most recent progress in antibody-epitope structure prediction has been achieved by AF2 and related approaches.¹²³ Initial exploration of AF-M, an extension of AF2 to protein complexes, indicated relatively poor performance in predicting

antibody and antibody-antigen structures.^{33,124} However, in late 2022, the AF developers released updated AF-M models (version 2.3.0), which show substantially improved antibody-antigen prediction accuracy in independent benchmarks.^{119,120} In these benchmarks, AF-M correctly predicted antibody-antigen complex structure in about 20%–50% of cases, depending on the exact approach and accuracy thresholds used. Notably, a 51% success rate was obtained by applying a modification called AFSample to AF-M that increases the number and diversity of generated candidate structures.^{120,125} The state of the art changed again in May 2024 with the publication of AF3, which was reported to show improved performance on the antibody-antigen prediction task, especially when many candidate structures are generated and ranked by model confidence. However, at the time of writing, AF3 is available only via a server with significant throughput and use restrictions.²⁴ Independent assessments of AF3 have so far been limited but are consistent with a substantial improvement over AF-M for this task.¹²¹

An alternative approach to predicting Ab-Ag structures using ML is to separately model the Ab and Ag structures and apply docking methods to generate the bound complex. Classic rigid-body docking methods include ClusPro¹²⁶ and ZDOCK.¹²⁷ More recently, ML models have also been developed for this task, such as DiffDock-PP¹²⁸ and tFold,¹²⁹ the latter allowing non-rigid-body movement. In this setting, the antibody and antigen unbound structures could be experimentally determined or predicted using AF or another model, like IgFold¹³⁰ or ImmuneBuilder.¹³¹ In one of the benchmarks referenced previously,¹¹⁹ a protocol that separately modeled the antigen and antibody using AF, then predicted the complex structure using ClusPro, was found to substantially underperform AF-M. However, the cases correctly predicted by each tool were distinct, i.e., the structures the ClusPro-based protocol was able to successfully predict were predicted incorrectly by AF-M. This suggests that combining binding prediction methods may improve accuracy. In line with this idea, an approach called AlphaRED that combines AF-M with physics-based docking was reported to achieve substantially improved accuracy on Ab/Ag docking over AF-M.¹²²

We anticipate that progress on antibody specificity prediction will benefit from further advances in protein structure prediction and the integration of multiple kinds of datasets for model training (Table 1). The general protein-protein interaction field has already made great progress by applying AF-M.^{132,133} In one study, a relatively simple method for ranking AF-M-predicted structures recapitulated approximately half of the known true interacting pairs with nearly zero false discoveries.¹³⁴ Tailoring such ranking methods to antibody/antigen structures is a reasonable next step. Additionally, AF-M itself can likely be improved for this task. For example, its use of multiple sequence alignments (MSAs) is likely suboptimal for antibodies (as well as for TCRs), which are subject to a unique form of generation (i.e., V(D)J recombination) and clonal selection.¹³⁵ The way AF-M (as well as AF3) handles templates (treating each chain separately) is also likely suboptimal given inter-chain dependencies,¹³⁶ an issue which some work is beginning to address.¹³⁷ As mentioned before, approaches for modeling conformational flexibility will likely also be particularly important to correctly modeling antibody CDR loops.^{138,139} Finally, many different kinds of data are

potentially applicable as training data for antibody specificity prediction, and no work we are aware of has attempted to bring them to bear on this problem simultaneously. To name a few, datasets of epitopes,⁵⁸ deep mutational scans,^{20,140–142} protein structures,^{54,55} receptor sequencing from methods like LIBRA-seq,^{143,144} high-throughput antigen profiling methods such as phage immunoprecipitation sequencing (PhIP-seq),¹⁴⁵ rapid extracellular antigen profiling (REAP),¹⁴⁶ or molecular indexing of proteins by self-assembly (MIPSA)^{143,147} (especially of monoclonal antibodies), the results of phage display or immunization-based antibody development campaigns,^{148,149} and perhaps even patents containing antibody sequences for known antigens,^{53,150} all likely contain usable signals for this problem. Each of these modalities has the potential to contribute distinct information for predictor training. For example, protein structures from the protein databank could provide the basis for generalization across antibodies and antigens, whereas deep mutational scans for a few antigens could force a predictor to be sensitive to the local geometry of the antibody/antigen interface and learn to correctly predict non-binding even for cases where very similar antibodies do bind a particular antigen. Between these extremes, LIBRA-seq¹⁴³ could provide many examples of BCRs for a handful of antigens, pushing a predictor to learn to model the diversity of antibodies binding a particular antigen. How best to integrate diverse information sources such as these is an important and open research topic.

RECEPTOR GENERATION

Receptor generation has been studied both from the perspective of biological simulation, aiming to generate realistic receptor sequences similar to what is found *in vivo* in naive repertoires, and from the standpoint of protein engineering, where the focus is on designing or improving an antibody or TCR to target specific epitopes. In this section, we discuss these two lines of work, as well as a few related tasks and perspectives.

Antigen-independent receptor generation

A line of research has focused on learning statistical models of V(D)J recombination based on TCR or BCR repertoire sequencing data (Figure 1E).^{151–156} For example, IGoR fits a probabilistic model to repertoire sequences, which can be used to assess the generation probability of sequenced receptors as well as sample new receptors.¹⁵¹ A key idea for these methods is to fit V(D)J recombination models to unproductive (out-of-frame) receptor nucleotide sequences, as these are not subject to post-V(D)J positive and negative selection processes. There has also been work in extending V(D)J recombination models to incorporate selection steps using productive (in frame) sequences.^{152,153,157} V(D)J recombination models have been shown to vary across individuals, which means that the same immune receptor sequence may have different generation probabilities in different individuals.^{153,158,159} We note that an important source of this variability is germline allelic variation at the immunoglobulin and TCR loci, which is associated with antigen-driven selection outcomes.^{135,160–162} Importantly, V(D)J recombination models can be used to identify antigen-experienced clones by quantifying the likelihood of observing clones in several individuals. Specifically, if the level of clonal sharing

among individuals is incompatible with V(D)J recombination statistics, the clones in question may have arisen due to antigen-driven convergent responses.^{67,163} Finally, the recombination models have been used to simulate immune receptors for AIRR-ML benchmarking.^{164,165}

Protein language models (PLMs) have also been explored for generating realistic receptor sequences at the protein level. PLMs are self-supervised models trained on an unlabeled training dataset of protein sequences by randomly masking out amino acids in each example and tasking the model to predict the identity of the masked residues, an approach used for pre-training LLMs like ChatGPT.^{166,167} Beyond the “fill-in-the-blank” task it was trained on, PLMs are useful because they learn sophisticated internal representations (embeddings), which can be extracted from the PLM and used as input to supervised models trained on smaller datasets. For example, the embeddings from the ESM2 PLM¹⁶⁸ were used as input to a structure prediction model to develop the ESMFold structure predictor.¹⁶⁸ Studies of immune receptors have applied PLMs to a range of problems, including sequence infilling,¹⁶⁹ humanization,¹⁷⁰ predicting antigen-specificity,^{171–174} predicting receptor structure,¹³⁰ and AIRR diversity analysis.^{175–177} An important question for these applications is how the training dataset composition (general proteins vs. receptors, paired or unpaired receptor chains, one or multiple species, whether similar sequences are collapsed to consensus sequences) impacts PLM utility for various tasks.¹⁷⁸

Interestingly, it was recently demonstrated that general protein PLMs are superior to PLMs trained exclusively on antibody sequences for some antibody optimization tasks.¹⁷⁹ On the other hand, other recent reports found that antibody PLM performance for binding prediction tasks improved when paired-chain information was used for training.^{172,180} A related issue is that existing PLMs have a germline bias, which may hinder them in exploring antibody sequences derived from somatic hypermutation (SHM).¹⁸¹ Finally, we note an intriguing report that a general protein PLM can predict antibody mutations that improve antigen binding without explicit knowledge of the antigen, although the mechanism here remains poorly understood.¹⁷⁹

Epitope-specific receptor design

The clinical importance of therapeutic antibodies has driven great interest in developing methods for computationally designing antibodies that bind specified epitopes. Although less work has focused on generating TCRs, similar ideas apply, and the opportunities for computationally generated T cell therapies (e.g., in oncology) are substantial. We focus on antibody generation here, but many ideas discussed apply to TCRs as well.

The development of therapeutic antibodies often involves iterative optimization of a candidate with the goal of identifying mutations that enhance antigen affinity or improve developability properties (Figure 1F). Deep mutation scanning (DMS) experiments based on mammalian display,²⁰ yeast display,^{182,183} or phage display^{184–186} have been used in this context to characterize the binding affinity of a large number of variants of a given antibody. While these studies can be performed without ML, a line of work has shown that their efficiency can be enhanced by using ML to model the mutational fitness landscape captured in the DMS experiment.^{20,182,184,187,188} The models are typically trained on

DMS data, then applied to generate designs to test for the next round of experiments.¹⁸⁹ Using off-the-shelf ML architectures, a useful level of accuracy is possible.¹⁸³ For example, an early study applying this methodology used a DMS dataset of variants of the anti-HER2 therapeutic antibody trastuzumab.²⁰ The authors trained a convolutional neural network on a one-hot encoding of the heavy-chain CDR3 sequence and achieved good accuracy (AUC = 0.91) at classifying if a sequence binds HER2. Among high-confidence predictions, 30 of 30 randomly selected designs were shown to bind HER2 experimentally. Traditionally, these models have focused on sequence alone, and a separate set of methods has tackled the scenario where a structure of the bound complex is available, but DMS data are absent.^{190–193} However, progress can likely be made by combining the growing number of DMS datasets^{141,142,183,194,195} with protein structure information to develop improved models for antibody-antigen binding.^{17,196} We also note that predictors of developability enable optimization of therapeutic antibodies for other important properties beyond binding affinity, such as solubility and immunogenicity.¹⁹⁷ Such multi-parameter optimization is challenging since many important parameters for developability are located in the variable region,^{3,197,198} and training data are scarce.^{149,199}

Before discussing *de novo* generation of antibodies (Figure 1G), we briefly review recent progress in general protein design methods. In the years since AF2 was released, dramatic advances have been made using deep learning to generate novel (non-antibody) proteins that bind arbitrary targets or have other user-specified properties.^{200–202} Several popular pipelines split the protein design task into two phases: structure design, in which the goal is to generate realistic protein backbones, and inverse folding, in which sequences predicted to fold into the specified backbone structure are generated.

For structure design, the three modeling avenues that have been explored so far are hallucination, diffusion, and flow matching.²⁰³

- (1) Hallucination methods use a structure prediction model such as AF2 and iteratively optimize an initially random input sequence to have a predicted structure with the desired properties. A notable example of a hallucination-based pipeline is BindCraft, which reports state-of-the-art experimental success rates (~50%) for binder design.²⁰⁰
- (2) Denoising diffusion probabilistic models are trained to recover training examples after perturbation by varying amounts of random noise. The trained model can be used to generate new examples from the same distribution as the training set by iteratively de-noising starting from pure noise. RFDiffusion^{25,201} and Chroma²⁰⁴ are diffusion-based protein design methods.
- (3) Flow matching models are a more general approach than diffusion models that are gaining in popularity, in which a direct mapping is learned from a simple distribution (e.g., Gaussian) to the data distribution. Flow matching-based tools for protein design are currently less mature, but several methods have been proposed.^{205,206}

After a structure has been generated using any of these methods, an inverse folding model is typically used to sample

a sequence predicted to fold to the desired structure. The most commonly used method for this task is ProteinMPNN,²⁰⁷ which is a graph neural network trained to recapitulate sequences from the backbone structures of proteins in the PDB.

Typical protein design workflows will generate many candidate sequences using structure design and inverse folding, then apply a series of filtering and ranking criteria to select the designs for experimental testing. A key filtering approach most pipelines use is evaluation using a structure predictor (such as AF2 or RoseTTAFold) that is independent from the model used to generate the designs.²⁰⁸

Despite the promise of recent protein design methods, it is not possible to generate antibodies using these methods, as they typically can generate only a single-chain protein. More fundamentally, the interaction interfaces of the generated proteins usually have stable secondary structures (often helical) rather than the flexible loops that antibodies use to contact the antigen. Antibody design thus requires specialized methods.^{209–211} The best progress to date on this problem has been made by fine-tuning the RFDiffusion²⁰¹ model on antibodies and similar protein complexes, then generating CDR sequences using ProteinMPNN.^{207,211} However, the binders were relatively weak, and the experimental success rates were low, requiring the screening of thousands of designs. Additionally, the method can only generate single-domain nanobodies rather than antibodies. Furthermore, at the time of writing, this work is a preprint without publicly available code or model weights.

Benchmarking is a key challenge for receptor design. In contrast to structure prediction models, which can be evaluated retrospectively on experimentally determined structures held out from the training set, generative models for immune receptor design must be evaluated after the models have been developed and used to generate predictions. This has the practical consequence that developers of generative models must collaborate closely with experimentalists (or participate in contests) or rely on computational oracles that remain imperfect.^{3,212}

Furthermore, the experimental evaluations can easily become cumbersome because in a benchmarking scenario, each model will generate a distinct set of designs to test, and the data collection requirements thus scale with the number of models being tested. There are also statistical challenges in experimental prospective evaluation, as a typical workflow usually involves the expression and testing of perhaps 10^1 – 10^3 binders.^{20,211,213} While such numbers of expressed antibodies are limited by experimental constraints,^{6,10} statistical problems can arise from the number of expressed antibodies given the potential number of receptors that can be generated by the generative ML method (or the true underlying diversity of biologically possible sequences with that property). We illustrate this point in a thought experiment. Briefly, generative models are trained on sequences with a given property (e.g., HIV binding). Once trained, the model's task is to generate novel HIV-binding sequences that differ from those in the training dataset. To demonstrate that the ML approach can generate sequences with the desired function, the current state-of-the-art is to test experimentally up to 10^3 ML-generated sequences to evaluate the ML approach.

With very simplified assumption, one can show (see [Text S1](#)) that to have confidence interval limits within $\pm 5\%$ of the estimate, one must test between 139 and 385 sequences at least,

depending on the proportion of sequences in the list with the property ([Figure S1](#); [Text S1](#)). If one is willing to accept interval limits within $\pm 10\%$ of the estimate, one still needs between 62 and 97 sequences at least. For $n = 50$ sequences to be sufficient, one would have to accept an interval up to $\pm 14\%$, which corresponds to a large uncertainty about the actual proportion of sequences with the desired property ([Figure S1](#); [Text S1](#)). It should also be noted that this analysis provides a measurement for the proportion p of sequences with the property among the list of ML-generated sequences, which may differ from the proportion p^* of sequences with the property in the generative model, where p and p^* can be seen as the quality of the list and the generative model, respectively. The reason for this is that some sequences may be drawn repeatedly by the ML model, whereas others are drawn rarely, but each sequence appears at most once on the list. We have illustrated this in the [Text S1](#). In brief, p could be more than 5 times as large as p^* , in particular if a large fraction of sequences in the list are likely to have the property or the probability of having the property varies a lot among ML-generated sequences.

To summarize, current experimental evaluations are not grounded in statistical power analyses. More elaborate power analyses than the thought experiment described above are needed to evaluate whether a given experimental evaluation experiment is sufficient to validate the true positive generation rate of a generative ML approach. Indeed, in the above thought experiment, we assumed only one generative ML method. In theory, there could be many tests in parallel, such as in benchmarking studies, thus increasing the required number of evaluations for sufficient power.

Other ideas and approaches

As mentioned previously, generative models for protein design are typically applied by sampling sequences from the model, synthesizing DNA coding for each sequence, and screening for the desired functionality (e.g., antigen binding). In the context of high-throughput display assays, the limiting factor in terms of the number of designs tested is often the DNA synthesis step. Recent work has attempted to address this using stochastic DNA synthesis. The idea, termed “variational synthesis,” is to train a computational model whose parameters correspond to experimental conditions.^{214,215} Briefly, the parameters for a simple model of DNA oligo synthesis might be the fraction of each nucleotide to incorporate at each position in a sequence. After training the model on a very large number of observed sequences (e.g., from a protein design model), the parameters can be used to synthesize a vast library of designs that recapitulates the training set as closely as possible. For example, a variational synthesis model fit to observed human antibody heavy-chain CDR3 sequences was used to generate $\sim 10^{17}$ CDR3 sequences *in vitro*.²¹⁵ In this demonstration, variational synthesis is similar to earlier work on degenerate codon library design to match specified amino acid frequencies,^{216,217} but, in theory, the highly general framework of variational synthesis can handle more sophisticated synthesis protocols, such as those involving stochastic assembly of longer sequences from shorter ones. We note, however, that the match between the synthesized sequences and the target sequences is only approximate, and a suitably high-throughput screening method is required.

Finally, we previously argued that ideas from linguistics, a field specialized in analytical rule extraction, can potentially aid in building more interpretable PLMs that are more likely to learn relevant domain-specific rules.^{218,219} Incorporating linguistic ideas into PLMs may enable the development of next-generation interpretable ML models with the potential of uncovering the biological mechanisms underlying sequence-function relationships (i.e., rules). In this context, rules may be defined as the syntactic and semantic lexicons that compose the AIR language. With this definition framework in place, it may be possible to refine the current simplified encoding schemes^{17,220} by incorporating non-linear (interaction²²¹) relationships and fitness landscapes.^{222–226} More generally, PLMs are said to understand the “grammar” of protein sequences, but few studies have investigated whether grammar, in the sense of natural language, exists in proteins (or antibodies) in the first place.^{218,219,227,228} By comparing AIR sequences with human language in terms of linguistically defined grammar and semantics, we found that there are similarities and dissimilarities between human language and AIR sequences.^{218,229}

REPertoire CLASSIFICATION

ML applied to AIRRs is gaining attention for its potential to be a powerful diagnostic tool for immune and infectious conditions (Figure 1H). Notable examples of the applications of ML-aided repertoire classification are the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA)-approved diagnostic tool T-detect COVID,²³⁰ and the recently available T-detect Lyme for early diagnosis of Lyme disease.^{231,232} For a detailed overview of ML-aided immune repertoire classification and its applications, see recent review articles.^{1,7} Here, we focus on the assumptions of AIRR-ML methods as well as the knowledge needs and challenges of the field.

While achieving a clinically deployable level of performance for diagnostics is one of the ultimate goals of the AIRR-ML field,²³³ the identification of immune state-associated sequences that act as explanatory features for the prediction task may have important implications for immunotherapeutics and vaccine design. Here, we first summarize the assumptions of state-of-the-art AIRR-ML models for the immune state classification problem. Following, we discuss the knowledge needs and challenges for the AIRR-ML field in the context of both diagnostics and therapeutics while relating these to the operating assumptions of AIRR-ML models and contemporary study design characteristics.

Operating assumptions of the state-of-the-art AIRR-ML models for immune state classification problem

Rather than focusing on individual ML methods, a unified view of the operating assumptions (i.e., prior assumptions) of state-of-the-art AIRR-ML methods can provide a concise summary of the information encoded in repertoire data in various observed or latent forms that can help discriminate the labels of distinct immune states. The operating assumptions of a large majority of the contemporary AIRR-ML approaches can be categorized as being similar to one or more of the below assumptions:

- (1) Repertoire diversity: the diversity of receptor sequences within repertoires (as quantified by various entropy mea-

- asures) can distinguish different immune states (e.g., Greiff et al.²³⁴).
- (2) Differential gene usage: differential gene usage (e.g., V genes) can distinguish immune states (e.g., Bashford-Rogers et al.,²³⁵ Roskin et al.,²³⁶ Davis et al.,²³⁷ Bolen et al.,²³⁸ and Zaslavsky et al.²³⁹).
- (3) Identical public clones: identical receptor sequences are shared between repertoires of a shared disease or phenotype (referred to as public clones). They can be observed with increased frequency in the immune state of interest relative to some control group of repertoires or more than expected by chance. Repertoires with a particular condition carry an excess of such condition-associated public clones (e.g., Emerson et al.,³⁶ Akerman et al.,²⁴⁰ and Pogorelyy et al.²⁴¹).
- (4) Sequence-similar public clones: public “clones” do not necessarily have to be identical. Similar receptor sequences (defined by some sequence distance metric) are shared between repertoires of a disease or phenotype and can be observed with increased frequency in the immune state of interest relative to some control group of repertoires or more than expected by chance. Repertoires with a particular condition carry an excess of such condition-associated “sequence-similar” public clones (e.g., Dash et al.,¹⁸ Glanville et al.,¹⁹ Zaslavsky et al.,²³⁹ and Zhang et al.²⁴²).
- (5) Functionally similar public clones: “similar” public clones do not necessarily have to be “sequence-similar,” rather, they can be “functionally similar,” which can be determined by the similarity of receptor sequences in some model-derived latent representational space (e.g., Zaslavsky et al.,²³⁹ Akerman et al.,²⁴⁰ and Widrich et al.²⁴³).
- (6) Abundance of public clones: the abundance (clonal counts) of public receptor sequences (identical or similar) within individual repertoires contribute significantly to the discrimination of immune states (e.g., Widrich et al.²⁴³).
- (7) Enriched sub-sequence patterns: certain short sub-sequence patterns (k-mers or similar) can be immune state-associated based on their elevated frequency in the immune state of interest relative to some control group of repertoires or more than expected by chance (e.g., Cinelli et al.,²⁴⁴ Sun et al.,²⁴⁵ Thomas et al.,²⁴⁶ Ostmeyer et al.,²⁴⁷ and Katayama and Kobayashi²⁴⁸).
- (8) Weighted clonal counts for patterns: incorporation of the clonal count information as some form of weights when associating short sub-sequence patterns (described in 7) with immune states can contribute significantly to the discrimination of immune states (e.g., Ostmeyer et al.²⁴⁷ and Katayama and Kobayashi²⁴⁸).
- (9) Location of enriched patterns: where the enriched sub-sequence patterns occur within the receptor sequences is an important contributor to the discrimination of immune states.
- (10) Functional similarity of amino acids: consideration of the functional similarity of amino acid residues as captured by substitution matrices or other summaries (e.g., Atchley factors, BLOSUM distances) can improve the definitions of similar clonotypes (e.g., Dash et al.,¹⁸ Zhang et al.,²⁴² and Ostmeyer et al.²⁴⁷).

Toward a universal repertoire classification model Need for integrating operating assumptions for diverse immune state prediction

Studies of immune responses in different immune states have observed a variety of adaptive immune repertoire characteristics associated with these immune states, such as changes in sequence diversity,²³⁴ gene usage,^{235–239} CDR sequence lengths,^{235,249} SHM rates,^{250,251} and the harboring of identical^{36,240,241} or similar public sequences^{18,19,239,242} or condition-associated motifs.^{244–248} ML method developers may selectively integrate such observations as operating assumptions when crafting algorithms tailored for specific diseases or phenotypes (e.g., through feature engineering). However, immune responses across different conditions (e.g., infections, autoimmune diseases, and cancers) can be quite heterogeneous, where epitope-specific sequence diversity and immune responses visible at the repertoire level may drastically differ. Consequently, ML methods optimized for one immune state, due to specific operating assumptions, may not readily generalize across others. For broad clinical applications, future models should consider and encapsulate the full spectrum of operating assumptions, possibly through ensemble approaches that strive for a universal model capable of handling various immune states as well as technical variation.^{239,252}

Need for generalizing well from small datasets and to unseen classes

One of the challenges for repertoire classification methods is to generalize well from studies of small cohorts.^{165,248} There is a need to definitively solve this challenge, as most studies curated in AIRR-seq databases have a sample size of less than a hundred. For instance, <5% of the studies in the iReceptor database⁴⁹ have a sample size >100 (as of 27 May 2024). In recent years, few-shot learning has emerged as a promising solution that utilizes prior knowledge to improve generalization from limited examples.²⁵³ There are different ways to incorporate prior knowledge, such as augmenting training data, constraining the hypothesis space, or altering the search strategy in the hypothesis space.²⁵³ However, there is limited knowledge of which approach is most promising for the AIRR domain. Nevertheless, our recent work²⁵⁴ on incorporating prior knowledge by altering the search strategy in the hypothesis space has shown that the few-shot learning approach can successfully generalize, even when learning from fewer examples (with a 30-fold reduction in dataset size). Future research should explore alternative ways of implementing few-shot learning for various immune responses and signal complexities to determine which approach works best for the AIRR classification problem.

Another dilemma for repertoire classification models is what to do when encountering immune states that were not observed during training or when the evidence to make a prediction is inconclusive. For effective diagnostic purposes, it is preferable for models to refrain from making predictions when the evidence is insufficient (e.g., Zaslavsky et al.²³⁹). In addition, being able to learn meta-knowledge across a wide range of tasks (e.g., being able to learn generic information related to changes in repertoires as a response to different types of infections, autoimmunity, cancer, and age-related changes) and using such meta-knowledge to assign a label to examples belonging to classes unseen during the training process can also be useful in diagnos-

tics and a useful direction for the AIRR-ML field. Such a meta-learning approach has been proposed recently for receptor-level prediction models.²⁵⁵

Need for leveraging repertoires for accurate receptor- level annotation models

Annotating receptor sequences with their targets could greatly benefit vaccine design, diagnostics, and therapeutics.^{256,257} However, challenges include the vast diversity of these sequences²⁵⁶ and the low sensitivity of current experimental methods,²⁵⁸ leading to limited existing knowledge about epitope specificity in public databases.⁹⁰ Because repertoire-level data are relatively inexpensive and contain a greater number of receptors in weakly labeled (donor immune state) datasets,⁴⁹ they may enhance the rate and throughput of receptor-level annotation. Recent studies have suggested the possibility of identifying distinct label-associated features simultaneously from the same repertoire dataset through generative modeling (e.g., to disentangle age-, HIV-, CMV-, and type 1 diabetes-associated features from the same dataset).^{259,260} The benefit of such generative models is not only their ability to annotate receptors with labels but also their capacity to synthesize similar, novel label-associated features. Nevertheless, to use such approaches for either of these purposes on a large scale, a comprehensive evaluation of the ability of such models is also needed across a wide range of immune responses (labels) and signal complexities. A key concern in receptor-level annotation using repertoire-level data is the potential confounding from demographic factors such as age, gender, or other systematic biases. We and others have recently demonstrated that causal reasoning can help identify confounders that potentially need to be addressed in model construction,^{261,262} thereby improving the generalizability of ML models.

TCR recognition of peptides presented on MHC (encoded by HLA loci in humans) is restricted by the specific combinations of peptide and MHC.²⁶³ The polymorphic nature of HLA genes, their varying allele frequencies across populations, and the HLA molecules exhibiting specificity for binding certain peptides mean that ignoring the HLA poses challenges for annotating TCR specificity. On the other hand, as individuals sharing the same HLA allele and exposed to the same antigens may share similar TCR sequences, recent studies have demonstrated that public TCR sequences to common exposures can be detected in an HLA-restricted fashion.^{66,264} Knowledge of the association between TCRs and the specific peptide-HLA combinations can be used to fine-tune the annotation of receptor sequences in terms of antigen specificity. These studies have demonstrated that such knowledge can predict the HLA types of individuals with good accuracy from TCR sequence data alone.^{264,265} Consequently, all the historical repertoire data from public databases can be used to infer the HLA types of individual subjects, which in turn can be used when analyzing antigen-specificity through the lens of HLA restriction to fine-tune the models of TCR specificity.

WHAT IS NEEDED FROM THE AIRR FIELD TO MAKE PROGRESS ON AIRR-ML ALGORITHMS?

Improved transparency, efficiency, and collaboration in AIRR-ML development

For the scientific community to effectively reuse or peer-review AIRR-ML methods, the methods need to be shared in a manner

that is reproducible and transparent. To address this need, we developed immuneML, an open-source software ecosystem that enables efficient, reproducible, and interoperable AIRR-ML methods.¹⁶⁵ Incorporating best practices from software engineering and ML is vital, as is optimizing performance. To expedite method development within the AIRR-ML field, there is a need to increase the sharing of knowledge and resources within the field. For example, storing and reusing pre-trained models developed by others can be useful, as attempted in the genomics field.²⁶⁶ The aforementioned aspects can be effectively addressed by embracing and adopting domain-specific ML and analysis platforms (e.g., Pavlović et al.¹⁶⁵).

Benchmarking, simulations, and competitions

Current AIRR-ML models are data-starved (Table 1). More data—including broader sequence and structure-based coverage of epitopes and antigens as well as deep coverage of mutational landscapes—would increase prediction accuracy and interpretability. Current available dataset sizes are limited, with only 10^4 – 10^5 unique sequences available for receptor specificity tasks^{20,90,183,267} and 10^3 – 10^5 per repertoire for repertoire diagnostics tasks.^{36,268} However, what is less appreciated is that the lack of available data also holds back progress in methodology development. Critical and comprehensive comparisons of method performance are essential for guiding the direction of new methodology development in the field.

A broad range of methodologies has recently been proposed for receptor specificity and repertoire diagnostics prediction, as reviewed above. There is, however, no clear consensus on which of the explored methodological directions are most promising. A main limitation is that the size of available data both in terms of overall breadth as well as per-epitope coverage does not provide sufficient statistical power to robustly discern true underlying performance differences from chance. This is compounded by the fact that true underlying performance may vary between contexts, making it challenging to determine how broadly any method performance difference would generalize. Finally, the way experimental data is currently compiled and combined for ML training and assessment is, in general, quite artificial. For example, combining positive and negative instances from separate experimental sources and settings can lead to very artificial problem definitions (e.g., “which of K particular epitopes is a given receptor binding to given that one knows it is binding exactly one of them”)⁸¹ or introduce spurious relations (confounding) that ML methods can exploit through shortcut learning.²⁶¹

A separate, and also underappreciated, challenge is that methodologies that work well on future large datasets may well vary fundamentally from methodologies that work well on currently available small datasets. As an example, modern components of deep learning like long short-term memory (LSTM) networks,²⁶⁹ only showed their full potential after sufficiently sized datasets became available.²⁷⁰ This raises the risk that current dataset size limitations would guide AIRR methodology development in a direction that is not fruitful for the data availability sizes we anticipate for the field in the future (Figure 2).

We have recently argued that the use of simulated data is a useful way to counter the issues arising from current experimental data limitations.^{99,270,271} AIRR-specific simulations

exist^{151,164,272} and have been applied for various applications in computational AIRR research.^{159,273–275} Indeed, better simulation frameworks are not only sought in AIRR but also in other fields.^{276–279} While the AIRR field and, more generally, the computational biology field are catching up with the need for simulations,^{270,276–280} we see the predominant reliance on wet-lab experimentally derived data for evaluating methods as an impediment to high-quality tool development, ultimately diminishing our understanding of biology.²⁷⁰ Beyond the above-described issues connected to dataset size limitations, the overreliance on experimental data ignores the fact that for experimental data, the experimental noise, due to, for example, limitations of primer sets, is mostly unknown or not accounted for. Furthermore, the ground truth—here defined as the knowledge of the generative principles of a given entity—is unavailable, and experimental data cannot be generated without constraints, allowing only limited benchmarking of whether a given method returns reliable biologically relevant information.

While the use of simulated data can help in overcoming the above-discussed limitations of experimental data, especially related to dataset size and access to fine-resolution ground truth, it does bring its own set of challenges. Similar to experimental data, simulated data can suffer from unintended shortcut learning opportunities.²⁸¹ More crucially, to ensure that the simulated data are relevant and representative of the underlying biology of interest, a simulation scheme needs to reflect core problem aspects at a sufficient level of fidelity.²⁷⁰

More generally, with the complexity of AIRR biology, there is a need for high-throughput experimental technologies that can evaluate ML predictions. There is also a need for unbiased interpretability and explainability approaches that can link AIRR features to prediction performance.^{99,243,282} Ultimately, the goal of AIRR-ML approaches is not just prediction accuracy but also the discovery of new biological insights.

To make progress on AIRR-ML technology, the development of platforms and software infrastructure is essential to enable broad reproducibility and interoperability of ML approaches.^{283,284} We have previously published the immuneML ecosystem,¹⁶⁵ which not only enables readily running several ML methods using standardized parameters but also interconnectivity with databases^{51,52} such as the iReceptor database.^{49,285} Indeed, while there exist public databases with AIRR data (annotated with metadata), these databases are not AI-ready. For now, it remains inconvenient to run methods on large-scale investigations—data need to be conveniently available (e.g., MNIST is immediately available).

These AI-ready data are required for unbiased competitions, which can help identify blank spots in current ML methods, map out future challenges, refocus data generation on unresolved problems,²⁸¹ refine simulation frameworks, and draw in fresh new ideas from AIRR-unrelated areas. Ideally, the benchmarking is carried out at regular intervals²⁸⁶ or continuously, as done previously for other methodological challenges.²⁸⁷ A combination of suited experimental and simulated benchmark datasets is an essential need for benchmarking since each offers distinct advantages and drawbacks as stated above. To summarize, the AIRR-ML field is now at a juncture where convenient availability of complementary data sources, combined with reproducibility and systematic

Figure 2. The path toward a generalizable model for AIR-epitope interactions

Developing a generalizable model of affinity between AIR and their cognate antigens would revolutionize the biomedical field. However, existing computational approaches generalize poorly due to limited data availability. Furthermore, even in instances where data exist, the absence of standards and collaborative endeavors impedes the objective evaluation and recognition of the limitations of current methods. A focused collaborative effort to establish standardized, openly accessible large-scale datasets enabling unbiased public competitions can pave the way forward.

benchmarking, could provide invaluable insights into the current methodologies and inspire a new wave of innovative method development.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES: HOW TO DISCOVER NEW AIRR BIOLOGY WITH AI

While the majority of published AIRR-ML research has focused, in a broad sense, on various aspects of optimizing prediction accuracy with respect to a certain ML task, the ultimate aim of

AIRR-ML—understanding the underlying principles of AIRR biology (e.g., molecular rules of antigen binding)—has, in our opinion, so far been mostly secondary. We believe that better integration of biological and computational AIRR research will lead to faster progress in the discovery of novel AIRR biology. Indeed, breakthroughs in related fields (e.g., computational structure prediction²³) have influenced some aspects of AIRR research (for example, enabling large-scale structure-based antibody profiling²⁸⁸). However, the core problems that hold back AIRR-ML research, and thus, biological insight into AIRR

biology, are the lack of standardized annotated large-scale datasets and large-scale competitions⁸¹ for well-defined problem setups, which could consistently guide development toward blank spots in methodology. Establishing a suite of formally defined standard problems for the field will be an important first step in this direction, as it will allow side-by-side comparison of method performance on identically defined tasks while also allowing methods to explicitly aim for complementarity rather than direct improvement by proposing variations to the established tasks. Such a suite of formal problems with accompanying datasets and assessment criteria for each could allow method development in the AIRR field to systematically branch out to cover a multitude of interesting variations in the same way as with the multiple *de facto* standardized MNIST variations in the image analysis field.^{289–292}

Currently, most repertoire classification approaches rely on antigen-agnostic features,^{1,273} which is likely insufficient to comprehensively describe AIRR biology. Reliable binding prediction to many epitopes would constitute a revolution in the AIRR field. We should seek to develop a generalizable model instead of focusing on smaller and more defined incremental projects. To enable universal epitope-specific predictors, the involvement of large-scale funding mechanisms is required, where considerable funding is focused on a specific defined research question (e.g., Chan-Zuckerberg Biohubs,²⁹³ Cancer Grand Challenges,²⁹⁴ ARPA-H,²⁹⁵ and Focused Research Organizations²⁹⁶) (Figure 2). The success of AF2 has shown that creating an ecosystem around a central question is crucial to solving questions that are ultimately data-limited. Indeed, we believe there is a consensus that AIR prediction can be solved given sufficient data, as a remarkable extent of predictability of AIRR biology has already been discovered.^{17–19,44,151} Furthermore, it is obvious that once this hurdle has been taken, even more challenging unresolved questions appear, such as the prediction of the adaptive immune response, personalized vaccination, and immunotherapy. Integration of AIR-antigen binding prediction with other parameters (e.g., transcriptome) will be needed for that.^{297–302} We also note that all binding prediction tasks discussed in this work focus on protein binding, while, e.g., for antibodies, binding prediction to glycans³⁰³ and lipids³⁰⁴ remain equally formidable challenges.

Finally, to efficiently drive AIRR-ML research forward, there must be more cross-talk between BCR and TCR research. For example, it is surprising that the TCR field has not yet embraced computational structure prediction like the BCR field. Vice versa, while the TCR field has access to curated databases that are one of the prerequisites for launching competitions,^{48,50,90,305} there is less curated epitope-specific BCR sequence data.⁴⁸ To summarize, we believe that collaborative research coordination,^{306,307} as, for example, exemplified in the single-cell field by the Human Cell Atlas (HCA) initiative,³⁰⁸ is key to breakthroughs in the AIRR field. Galvanizing initiatives such as the AIRR-Community³⁰⁹ exist and may be crucial to implementing HCA-like successes in the AIRR field.

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V.G. declares advisory board positions in aiNET GmbH, Epicom B.V., Absci, Omniscope, and Diagonal Therapeutics. V.G. is a consultant for Adaptive Biosystems, Specifica Inc., Roche/Genentech, Immunai, LabGenius, and FairJourney Biologics. T.J.O., G.I., J.P.L., R.A.B., R.A.A., and V.G. are employees of Imprint LLC. T.J.O. is a consultant for CDI Labs.

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Supplemental information

**Reading the repertoire: Progress in adaptive
immune receptor analysis using machine learning**

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Supplementary Text

Let n be the number of sequences one would have to test experimentally to obtain an estimate of p that is precise enough and thus trustworthy, where p is the true proportion among the list of generated sequences that have the desired property, for instance, HIV-binding. A natural measure for the precision of the estimate is half the width of a 95% confidence interval for p . If the n sequences to be tested experimentally are drawn at random from the list of ML-generated sequences, the number of sequences among these that have the property in question is approximately binomially distributed with parameters n and p . Note that this approximation requires that n is much smaller than the length N of the list of generated sequences. Based on the assumption of binomial distribution, the standard Wald confidence interval is given by $\hat{p} \pm 1.96\sqrt{\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})/n}$, where \hat{p} is the maximum likelihood estimator of p , namely the ratio of sequences with the property among the selected n . Note that the Wald interval assumes that \hat{p} approximately follows a normal distribution, which is a decent approximation as long as $n \cdot p$ and $n \cdot (1 - p)$ are both at least equal to 10. Given the formula for the confidence interval, one can easily compute the minimum required n to obtain a certain precision of the estimate of p , here quantified as the distance from the estimate to either of the interval limits, i.e., half the width of the interval. If the confidence interval limits should be within $\pm 5\%$ of the estimate, the computations show that one must test between 139 and 385 sequences, at least, depending on the proportion of sequences in the list with the property (see the figure below). If one is willing to accept interval limits within $\pm 10\%$ of the estimate, one still needs between 62 and 97 sequences at least. For $n=50$ sequences to be sufficient, one would have to accept an interval up to $\pm 14\%$, which corresponds to a large uncertainty about the actual proportion of sequences with the desired property (Figure S1).

Figure S1. The width of a 95% confidence interval for the proportion p of sequences with the desired property depends on both the estimate \hat{p} of p and on number n of sequences that are tested experimentally. The figure shows the needed n for the limits of the confidence interval to be at a distance of at most 5% (black), 10% (dark blue), 15% (turquoise) and 20% (light blue) from the estimate. One clearly sees that a narrow confidence interval, and thus an accurate estimate of p requires testing a rather large number of sequences.

As mentioned earlier, the proportion p of sequences with the property among the list of ML-generated sequences could differ substantially from the proportion p^* of sequences with the property in the generative model. To illustrate this, we consider a simplified setting where the marginal distribution of a given sequence occurring $p(x) = P(X = x)$ is approximately uniform, so that the generation probability $P(X = x | Y = 1)$ in the ML model is proportional to the probability $P(Y = 1 | X = x)$ that the given sequence has the property of interest. Further, we assume that the total number of different sequences that may be drawn from the ML model is 10^{11} . Moreover, we assume that generated sequences can be divided into two groups according to their probability of having the property, where k of them have a high probability p_1 , and the remaining ones have a much lower probability p_2 . In addition, we assume that k is much smaller than the number N of ML-generated sequences on the list. Under these assumptions, the k sequences with a high probability of having the property also have a much higher probability of being drawn from the ML model, and are therefore (almost) certain to be on the list. Then, p^* and p are approximately $\frac{k}{10^{11}} \cdot p_1 + \frac{10^{11}-k}{10^{11}} \cdot p_2$ and

$\frac{k}{N} \cdot p_1 + \frac{N-k}{N} \cdot p_2$, respectively. In the figure below (Figure S2), we have plotted the fraction p^*/p as a function of k/N , which is the proportion of sequences on the list having a high probability of having the property, for different values p_1 and p_2 and $N=10^5$. We made the same computations for $N=10^4$ and $N=10^6$, and the corresponding lines coincided with the ones for $N=10^5$. This shows that p^* and p become quite different if k is relatively large compared to N or p_1 and p_2 are quite different, meaning that if there are relatively many sequences on the list with a high probability of having the property or this probability differs a lot between sequences. Further, p^* is always smaller than p , meaning that the proportion of sequences generated by the generative model that have the given property is smaller than the corresponding proportion among the sequences on the list.

Figure S2. The proportion p^* of sequences generated by the ML model that have the property may be quite different from the corresponding proportion p of sequences on the list. The figure shows the proportion p^*/p as a function of the proportion k/N of sequences on the list that have a high probability p_1 of having the property for different values of (p_1, p_2) , where p_2 is the probability of having the property for the remaining sequences, with (p_1, p_2) equal to either $(0.99, 0.01)$ (black), $(0.9, 0.1)$ (dark blue) and $(0.8, 0.2)$ (turquoise). It shows that p^* is smaller than p , and possibly much smaller if the proportion of sequences on the list with a high probability of having the property is high or if this probability differs substantially between sequences.